

Siddabarun Zamani: Daga Kimiyya da Fasaha Zuwa Dabarbarun Daburta Tunanin Bami

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Tsakure

Wannan ɗan bincike ya mayar da hankali ne kan nazartar tasirin zamani kan ayyukan siddabarun Bahaushe, musamman siddabarun ‘yan damfarara. Ya waiwaici sha’anin siddabarun Bahaushe a da, daga nan sai ya karkata zuwa ga nazarin tasirin zamani musamman kimiyya da fasaha a kan ayyukan na siddabaru. Waiwaitar yadda siddabaru ya kasance a da, ya bayar da hasken kaiwa ga nazarin yadda siddabaru yake kasancewa a yau. An dora aikin kan tunanin Bahaushe da ke cewa: “Karen bana shi ke maganin zomon bana.” An bi hanyoyi da dabarun gudanar da bincike da suka hada da hira da kuma kallace-kallacen bidiyoyin da suke d’auke da siddabarun zamani da aka gabatar a tarurruka daban-daban. An kuma nazarci wadansu fitattun rubuce-rubuce da aka gabatar kan siddabarun zamani. Binciken ya fahimci cewa, a yau al’ummar Hausawa ta waye ta yadda ba za a iya bin tsofaffin hanyoyin damfara a damfare ta ba. A ɓangare guda kuma, ana amfani da siddabarun zamani musamman ta taimakon kimiyya da fasaha wajen aiwatar da siddabaru da damfara a zamanance. Daga karshe binciken ya ba da shawarwarin cewa ya kamata a sanya kwas da ke magana game da siddabaru da damfara a jami’o’i domin wayar da kan al’umma don tsallake wa tarkon yaudara. A ɓangare guda kuma, tararrukan kara wa juna sani za su taka irin tasu muhimmiyar rawar wajen wayar da kan al’umma da fargar da su.

1.0 Gabatarwa

Daya daga cikin siffon al'ada shi ne sauyawa. Ayyukan siddabarun na daga cikin al'adun da al'ummomin duniya ke shan faman karo da su a harkokin rayuwarsu, cikin waɗannan al'ummu kuwa har da Hausawa. A matsayinsa na wani ɓangare na al'ada, siddabarun na samun sauye-sauye ta fuskoki daban-daban. Hakan kuwa dole ne ya ja hankalin dalibai da manazarta da masana al'ada. Shin 'yan siddabarun na gargajiya ne ke taka rawar kidan zamani wajen zamanantar da harkokinsu na siddabarun? Ko dai wasu ne daban da suka koshi da zamani ke shiga harka a matsayin haye? Ko ma dai yaya abin yake, tabbataccen al'amari ne cewa, 'yan siddabarun sun kasance masu dimbin hikima da fasaha. Ko banza dai tsantsar hikima suke amfani da ita wajen dabus tunanin bami.

Abubakar, (2007:23) ya rawaito cewa, tun wajejen 1995 shugaban kamfanin Microsoft' Bill Gates ya yi hasashen wani mataki da za a riska na dinkulewar duniya, ta yadda kowa zai iya sarafa bayanai da ilimin da ya shafi fannonin rayuwa daban-daban cikin sauki, kuma cikin takaitaccen lokaci. Ya yi wannan bayani ne cikin littafinsa mai suna *The Road Ahead*. Haƙiƙa wannan ya shafi ɓngarorin rayuwa gaba ɗaya. Daga ciki kuwa har da lamuran siddabarun da sihiri. Ana samun siddabarun da sihiri ne a zamantakewa da hulɗatayyar rayuwa ta yau da kullum. Wannan na nuna cewa, yayin da aka samu tsarin game duniya, su ma sha'anonin na siddabarun da sihiri za su sauya zane.

Wannan takarda za ta mayar da hankali wurin binciko ire-iren sauye-sauyen da aka samu a duniyar siddabarun Bahausha. A ciki ne za a duba ko zamani (musamman abin da ya shafi kimiyya da fasaha) ya yi tasiri a harkokin Hausawa na siddabarun? Baya ga haka, za a dubi yadda siddabarun ya kasance a duniyar yau. Kai-tsaye, za a nazarci wasu nau'o'in siddabarun da aka gudanar a manyan taruka musamman tarukan nuna baiwa na Amurka da na Biritish da na Larabawa da kuma na 'yan Cana (wato, *American Got Talent* da *British Got Talent* da *Arab Got Talent* da kuma *Chinese Got Talent*). A ire-iren waɗannan taruka, ana amfani da kimiyya da fasaha tare da zunzurutun dabaru irin na zamani yayin gudanar da ayyukan siddabarun.

1.1 Manufar Bincike

Wannan bincike na da kudurin nazartar sauye-sauyen da zamani ya kawo a duniyar siddabarun. Kai tsaye zai mayar da hankali kan:

- i. Waiwaitar siddabarun Bahausha a da.

- ii. Nazartar tasirin kimiyya da fasaha cikin ayyukan siddabaru.
- iii. Nazartar siddabarun Bahaushe a zamanin yau.

1.2 Ra'in Bincike

Wayo da dabara su suka mamaye duniyar siddabaru da damfara., su ne kuma ke jagorancin tafiyar. A bangare guda kuma, Bahaushe ya yi zarra a fagen wayo da hikima a duk duniyar bakar fata (Bunza, 2019).¹ A bisa waƙannan dalilai, za a iya hasashen cewa, siddabaru ba farariyar al'ada ba ce ga Bahaushe. Al'ada ce gadajjiya wanda binciken tarihintar zai kai ga binciken tarihin asalin Bahaushe na gaba ɗaya. Lura da haka, za a iya samun tunanin Bahaushe da ke wakiltar lamuransa na siddabaru da damfara. Wato ba sai an je kale daga wasu bangarorin ilimi na daban ba.

An ɗora wannan bincike bisa karin maganar Bahaushe da ke cewa: “Karen bana shi ke maganin zomon bana!” Bincike ya nuna cewa, mafi yawan waƙanda ake damfara ta hanyar siddabaru sun kasance masu ɗauke da ɗaya ko fiye na daga cikin halayen da ke kasa:

- i. Kwadafai.
- ii. Son banza.
- iii. Son abin duniya fiye da kima.

Ire-iren waƙannan ɗabi'u nasu ke ba wa ‘yan damfara damar rufe musu idanu ta hanyar ayyukan siddabaru da ke nuna cewa za su samu babbar riba. A duk lokacin da al'umma suka gane salailan siddabarun da ake amfani da su a damfara su, su kuwa masu yin siddabarun kan tanadi wasu sababbin dabarun da za su tafi da hankalin al'umma. Ke nan dai, karen bana sai ya yi maganin zomon bana kafin ya kubuta daga irin tanade-tanaden da ake masa. Amfani da abubuwan da zamani ya zo da su musamman na kimiyya da fasaha ya ba wa ‘yan siddabaru damar fito da sababbin hanyoyin damfarar ‘ya’yan zamanin.

1.3 Dabarun Bincike

Hausawa sun ce: “Ta wurin da fata ta fi taushi ta nan akan mayar da gaban jima.” Domin samun nagartaccen bincike, an bi manyan hanyoyi guda biyu a lokacin da ake tattara bayanannan wannan bincike. Hanya ta farko ita ce, tattaunawa (hira). An tattauna da masana al'adun Hausawa, musamman abin da ya shafi siddabaru da dangoginsa. Bayan nan kuma, an tattauna

¹Bunza, (2019) ya bayyana cewa: “A duk yankin Afirka al'umma guda ce ta yi kusa da wayon Bahaushe. Ita ce Asanti da ke kasar Ghana.” Ya bayyana wannan a hirar da aka yi da shi a shirin “Baƙonmu na Mako” a gidan rediyon FM da ke Gusau a Jahar Zamfara Nijeriya.

da wasu daga cikin waƙanda ke da kusanci da ilimin gani-da-ido kan lamuran siddabaru. An tattara bayanan da suka bayar tare da nazartar su bakin gwargwado.

Hanya ta biyu da aka yi amfani da ita kuwa ta shafi binciken intanet(*internet research/surfing*). An duba bidiyoyin siddabaru daban-daban waƙanda aka gudanar a manyan tarurrukan da aka gabatar a ƙasashe daban-daban. Daga cikinsu akwai:

- i. Bidiyoyin da ke ɗauke da siddabaru, waƙanda aka yi amfani da kimiyya da fasaha wajen shirya su.
- ii. Bidiyoyin da ke ɗauke da sirrin yadda aka gudanar da wasu fitattun siddabaru a manyan tarurrukan duniya.
- iii. Bidiyoyin da ke koyar da yadda ake amfani da kimiyya da fasaha domin aiwatar da siddabaru.
- iv. An kuma karanta littattafai da muƙalu da ke ɗauke da sirrikan yadda ake gudanar da wasu nau'ukan siddabaru, musamman na zamani.²

Domin layar binciken ta sami kyakkyawan rufi, da aka kammala nazarin ire-iren waƙannan bidiyoyi, an tattara bayanan da aka tsinto a cikin su tare da tsara su cikin aikin. Waƙannan hanyoyin da aka yi amfani da su a matsayin dabarun bincike, sun taimaka matuƙa wajen fito da sigogi da salailan siddabarun zamani tarwai tamkar tsaba a kan faifai.

2.0 Siddabaru a Duniyar Bahaushe ta Jiya da ta Yau

Dabara na nufin amfani da wayo da hikima da azanci. Jam'in dabara shi ne “dabaru.” Yayin da ka samu dabaru da yawa kuwa, musamman cikin salon da ka iya daburta tunanin mai kallo ko mai sauraro, sai masana suka kira shi da “siddabaru.” Bunza (2011:2-3)

2.1 Bahaushen Siddabaru a Da

A ra'ayin wannan bincike, tarihin samuwar siddabaru tsakanin Hausawa daɗaɗɗe ne, daɗewarsa da ta kai na tarihin Hausawan kansu. Dalili kuwa, daɗaɗɗen tarihin Bahaushe cike ya ke da misalan yadda ya shahara a fagen yin amfani da dabaru a abin da ya shafi al'amuran rayuwarsa daban-daban. Ana iya tsintar tsattsafin misalan waƙannan dabarbaru nasa cikin:

- i. Tatsuniyoyinsa.
- ii. Wasanninsa na gargajiya.
- iii. Almararsa.

²Waƙannan rubuce-rubuce sun haɗa da na Down, (1939); Hoffmann, (1980); Vere, (1981); Herlily, (2001); Gardner, (2014); Chiviriga, (2014) da makamantansu.

- iv. Rubuce-rubucen zubensa.
- v. Waƙoƙinsa na gargajiya.
- vi. Hikayoyinsa.
- vii. Tarihin gwagwarmayar Hausawa.

2.1.1 Siddabaru a Tatsuniyoyin Bahausha

A tatsuniyar zomo da kura da ‘ya’yanta, an ga tarin dabarbarun da zomo ya yi amfani da su. Tun lokacin da ya lura da kura daga bakin kogo take miƙa wa ‘ya’yanta abinci, a nan ya dana tarkon yi mata dabo ta hanyar siddabaru.³ Dabarar farko da ya yi shi ne, ya isa wurin ‘ya’yan na kura a matsayin baƙo. Haka kuma, ya ce ai sunansa “Ku Duka!”⁴ Zomo ya yi siddabaru na biyu yayin da ‘ya’yan kura ke fitowa daga kogon. Lokacin da ya tabbatar da asiri ya tonu, sai ya haɗe kunnuwansa biyu ya rufe fuskarsa, sannan ya ce da kura: “Riƙe mini takalmana kafin in fito.” Kura kuwa da ke hasale ta kama kunnuwan zomo ta yi wurgi da shi can gefe (a tunaninta takalma ne). Zomo ya tashi ya arce.⁵ A wata tatsuniyar makamanciyar wannan, kura ta yi amfani da ɗan botoromi guda ɗaya inda ta gabatar da shi a matsayin guda goma sha tara. Wannan kuwa ba tsafi ba ne, illa tsantsan dabaru, wato dai siddabaru.⁶

2.1.2 Siddabaru a Wasannin Gargajiya

Wasa dai na nufin duk wata magana da aka furta ko wani aiki da aka aikata da nufin raha da nishafi. Yayin da aka ce wasannin gargajiya kuwa, ana nufin wasannin Hausawa da suka kasance sanannu. Daga cikinsu akwai waɗanda suke da takamaiman wuri da lokacin aiwatarwa, wasu kuma har da sanannun kayan wasa da ake amfani da su yayin gudanar da wasannin.

A ɓangaren wasannin gargajiya, misalan siddabaru sun fi shurin masaki yawa. Akwai siddabaru da ya shafi yadda ake gudanar da wasannin kansu, akwai kuma waɗanda suka shafi waƙoƙin cikin wasannin. Za a tsinci irin wannan misalai na siddabaru yayin da aka nazarci wasan “Allah Raini.”⁷ Wasan a karan kansa yana da salo da siga na siddabaru. Dalili kuwa shi

³A nan zomo ya yi amfani da “lura” wanda kuwa ɗaya ce daga cikin fitattun halayen ɗan siddabaru.

⁴Wannan dabara ce irin ta ‘yan siddabaru tare da ɗimbin hangen nesa. Zomo ya san da cewa, duk lokacin da kura ta kawo abinci, to a dukkanin ‘ya’yan ta kawo wa.

⁵A nan zomo ya nuna wani hali na ‘yan siddabaru, wato “saurin nemo mafita ga matsala.”

⁶A duba rataye domin kallon tatsuniyar a kammale.

⁷Wannan ma wasa ne na dandali. Misalin yara biyar zuwa sama ne suke gudanar da wannan wasa. Yawan mutanen zai iya kai wa goma ko ma sama da haka. Yana tafiya da waƙa, sannan akan yi amfani da kayan wasa yayin gudanar da shi. Kasancewar wasan na dandali ne, an fi gudanar da shi da dare, musamman lokacin farin wata. Kayan wasan da ake tanada yayin gudanar da wasan su ne kallabi ko tsumma.

ne, ta shafi zurfafa tunani da amfani da dabaru domin gano inda wani ya buya (alhali kuwa idanuwan wanda zai yi wannan hasashe a rufe suke). Bayan nan, wasan ya shafi fayyace wanda ya tsallake Allah raini, alhali idanunsa na rufe. Hakika, kai tsaye za a iya kallon wannan a matsayin siddabaru.

Akan samu matakin siddabaru na gaba a cikin wannan wasa na Allah Raini yayin da aka yi amfani da dankore. Allah raini zai hada baki da wanda zai rufe masa idanuwa. Za su tanada wasu alamu na musamman da ke wakiltan dukkanin yaran da ke wasar. Misali (1):

1. Idan na taba kunnenka na dama, to Audu ne ya tsallaka ka.
2. Idan na taba kunnenka na hagu, to Musa ne ya tsallaka ka.
3. Idan na taba keyarka, to Balarabe ne ya tsallaka ka.

Yayin da aka yi wannan shiri, sai a tarar da cewa, nan da nan Allah raini zai gane duk wanda ya tsallaka shi. Bayan haka ma, Allah raini na amfani da daya ko fiye daga cikin ‘yan wasan a matsayin ‘yan kore. Misali (2):

Yadda Ake Wasa

Mutum daya zai zauna ya miƙe kafafunsa. Wannan shi ake kira Allah raini. Wani yaron kuma zai tsaya a bayansa ya rufe masa idanu. Idan ana amfani da kallabi ko tsumma, to da shi za a rufe idanu. Idan kuma babu, to akan rufe ne da hannuwa. Sauran yara kuwa za su jeru a layi. Daga nan wanda ya rufe wa Allah raini ido zai yi inkiya da baki cewa a taho a tsallaka kafafunsa. Yaron da ke tsaye a layi zai taho a hankali ya tsallaka shi. Daga nan kuma sai wanda ya rufe wa Allah raini ido ya tambaye shi:

“Allah raini wa ya tsallaka ka?”

Shi kuma zai ambaci sunan wanda yake tunanin shi ne ya tsallaka shi. Idan ya fada daidai, to zai tashi. Wanda aka ambaci sunan nasa kuwa zai zo ya zauna, wato ya zama Allah raini. Idan kuwa bai fadi sunan daidai ba, to wani daban zai zo ya tsallaka. Wani lokaci wanda ya rufe wa Allah raini ido zai iya ishara da baki cewa kada kowa ya tsallaka. Sannan sai ya tambaya Allah raini wanda ya tsallaka shi. A nan idan ya ce: “babu,” to ya yi nasara. Idan kuwa ya ambaci sunan wani daban, to ya fadi.

Idan yara suka gama tsallaka shi baki daya ba tare da ya gane wanda ya tsallaka shi ba, to wanda ya rufe masa ido zai ba da dama wa yara su je su buya. Yayin da yara suka buya, wanda ya rufe masa ido zai ambaci wuraren da suka buɓɓuya. Amma ba zai fayyace takamaimai wadanda suka buya a wuraren ba. Misali, wanda ya rufe wa Allah raini ido zai ce:

“Bayan bishiya, bayan dakali, gefen alamanke ...”

Sai kuma a tambayi Allah raini ya fadi sunayen wadanda suka buya a wadannan wurare. Shi kuwa zai yi kokarin yin hakan. Misali zai ce:

“Musa ne a bayan bishiya.”

Idan ya fada daidai to za a ce wa Musa:

“Taho bisa sayyadarka.”

Idan kuwa bai fada daidai ba, to za a ce Allah raini ya je ya goyo shi ya taho da shi.

Wasu Dokokin Wasa

- i. Duk wadda Allah raini ya ambaci sunansa bayan ya tsallaka shi (ya tsallaka Allah raini), to shi ne zai zama Allah raini.
- ii. Yayin da Allah raini ya fahimci ba a tsallaka shi ba, kuma ya fadi hakan, to wanda ya ki tsallakawar shi ne zai zama Allah raini.
- iii. Idan mutane suka gama Tsallake Allah raini ba tare da ya ambaci sunan kowa ba, to za su je su buya.
- iv. Yayin da Allah raini ya ambaci sunan wani dan wasa a matsayin ya buya a wani wuri, sai kuma aka yi rashin dace ba a nan ya buya ba, to zai je ya goyo wanda ke boye a wannan wuri.
- v. Wanda aka ambaci sunansa da wurin da ya buya, to shi ne zai zama Allah raini.

“Ni Danjummai zan tabbatar da cewa na tsaya a gaban Ciwake. Yayin da na zo tsallaka ka, to zan taba guiwarka da kafata. Mutumin da ke bi mini, zai kasance Ciwake, saboda haka sai ka ambaci sunansa.”

Wani wasan kuma da ake samun siddabaru shi ne “ wasan’yar Boyel.”⁸ Shi ma wannan wasan zubi da tsarinsa akwai hoton siddabaru a ciki. Dalili kuwa shi ne, ya shafi boye abu cikin hikima, tare kuma da yin amfani da hikima wurin gano abin da aka boye din. Bayan wannan, ɗaya daga cikin ‘yanwasan na iya shirya zamba a ransa. Yadda ake hakan kuwa shi ne, mai tafiyar⁹ zai ki sanya ‘yarsa¹⁰ a kowanne daga cikin tsubi-tsubin kasar. A maimakon haka, zai shammaci sauran ‘yan wasan ya boye ‘yar tasa a wani wuri. Yayin da abokan wasansa suka nuna tsibin kasar da suke tsammanin ‘yar ta ke, sai a ce ba nan ba ne. Idan sun duba kuwa za su tarar da lallai ba ta ciki. Shi kuma zai nuna musu ɗaya daga cikin sauran tsibi-tsibin kasar a matsayin nan ne ‘yar ta ke. A wannan lokacin ne kuma zai sake shammatansu ya sanya ‘yar a ciki. Da zarar an duba, sai a tarar da ita.

2.1.3 Almarar

A cikin almarar Bahausha ma akan tsinci misalan siddabaru, musamman waɗanda suka shafi lissafi. Daga cikin fitattun almarar Bahausha da ke ɗauke da misalan siddabaru akwai:

1. Almarar tsallake kogi tare da kura da akuya da dawa/ciyawa.¹¹
2. Almarar tafiya da rakuma huɗu a jere, waɗanda ɗaya na cin naman rakumi, ɗaya na cin naman mutum, ɗaya na cin kanwar bayan rakumi, ɗayan kuma lafiyarsa kalau.¹²

⁸Hanyar da ake gudanar da wannan wasa, yara ne za su yi tsubi-tsubin fasa kimanin uku ko huɗu ko sama da haka. Daga nan mai tafiya zai riƙe ‘yarsa da yatsu. Zai riƙa sanya hannunsa da gaggawa cikin wannan tsubi-tsubin fasa. Zai riƙa yi cikin gaggawa yadda ba za a riƙa ganin lokacin da zai bar ‘yar a ɗaya daga cikin tsubi-tsubin kasar ba.

A yayin da mai tafiya ke canza ‘yar daga tsubin fasa zuwa wani tsubin, zai fakii don abokan wasansa ya a je ‘yar a ɗaya daga cikin tsubin kasar. Sai kuma a cigaba da tamkar bai ajiye ‘yar tasa ba. Bayan ya kammala sai ya ba da dama ga bokin wasansa da ya nemo tsubin da ya bar ‘yarsa. Idan ya nuna daidai, to ya kwace saboda haka shi zai cigaba da tafiya. Idan kuwa bai nuna daidai ba, to wanda ke wasa ne zai cigaba.

⁹“Mai tafiya” a nan na nufin yaron da ke riƙe da ‘yar tafiya, wanda shi ne zai boye ta a wannan lokaci.

¹⁰A nan, “ya” na nufin tsakuwa ko wani abu mai kama da wannan, ita ce ake boyewa a cikin tsubin fasa.

¹¹Kai ne ka zo tsallake rafi, kuma kana tare da kura da akuya da dawa. Idan kana tare da su, kura ba za ta ci akuya ba, sannan akuya ba za ta ci dawa ba. Da zazar ka gusa kuwa, to kura za ta cinye akuya. Idan kuwa akuya da dawa aka bari, to akuyar za ta cinye dawa. A bakin rafin da za ku tsallake kuwa, kwale-kwale guda ne, sannan abubuwa biyu kacal zai iya ɗauka a lokaci guda. Wato zai iya ɗaukar mutum da kuma nau’in abu guda (ko kura ko dawa ko akuya). Saboda haka, dole ka tsallakar da abubuwan da kake tare da su ɗaya bayan ɗaya. To yaya za ka yi hakan ba tare da wata matsala ta samu ba?

¹²Wani falke ne wata rana ya shiga ruɗani. Ya dadɗe kwarai yana harkokin sa da rakuma, ya saba da sha’aninsu sosai. Amma wata rana sai maigidansa ya aike shi kai kanwa daga Agadas ta Nijar zuwa Sakkwato ta Nijeriya. Uku daga cikin rakuman nan kuwa na musamman ne. Domin ɗaya daga cikinsu, yana cin naman rakumi dan uwansa. Saboda haka, a duk lokacin da ake tafiya, idan dai a jere ne, dole ne ya kasance a gaba. Da zarar wani rakumi ya shiga gabansa, to zai cinye shi. Rakumi na biyu kuwa yana cin kanwa ne. Saboda haka, yayin da ake tafiya a jere, dole ne ya kasance a gaba, domin da zarar wani rakumi mai kanwa ya shiga gabansa, to zai cinye

3. Tsallakar da mayu uku tare da ‘ya’yansu ruwa.¹³

Dukkanin waɗannan almarorin wasa kwaƙwalwa (da ma wasu makamantansu), an yi amfani da dabarbaru na musamman yayin gina su. An samar da wani rikittaccen al’amari mai bukatar zurfafa nazari wajen warware shi. Da ma dai, ɗaya daga cikin ɗabi’un ɗan siddabaru shi ne “tsananin wayo.”

2.1.4 Hoton Siddabarun Bahaushe a Rubutun Zubensa

Rubutun zuben Bahaushe wani babban fage ne da ke tabbatar da cewa ya daɗe yana aiwatar da ayyukan siddabaru. Imam, (1998: 66-74) ya kawo hoton siddabaru ƙarara a littafin *Magana Jarice 2*. A cikin labarin “Jarabawar da aka yi wa Sarkin Barayi Nomau,” ya nuna wasu matakan siddabaru da Sarkin Barayi Nomau ya gabatar. Nomau ya nuna bajintar siddabaru yayin gudanar kasaitattun nau’o’in sata guda uku da aka sanya masa a matsayin gasa. Waɗanda suka ƙunshi satar zobe da ta bargon sarki, da kuma satar limamin gari sukutum.¹⁴

A littafin *Ruwan Bagaja*, an ga yadda Imam, (1999: 22) ya bayyana siddabarun da Abubakar ya gabatar a garin Tegi. Ta hanyar siddabarun ne ya yi maganin Sarkin Zagi da ya kasance yana damun sarkin garin Tegi kullum da dare. Ya yi dabarar shigewa ɗakinsa ba tare da ya ankara ba. Sannan ya bayyana gare shi a matsayin mutuwa. Kasancewar Sarkin Zagi bai tsammaci ganin wani mahaluki ba a wannan lokaci ya sa ya damfaru da cewar mutuwar ce da gaske.

2.2 Ko Siddabarun Bahaushe Ya Sanya Rigar Zamani?

Kamar yadda yake a tunanin Bahaushe cewa: “karen bana shi ke maganin zomon bana,” da alama wannan zomo na da saurin sauya salailan rayuwa. Hakan na nuna cewa, dole wannan

kanwar. Raƙumi na uku kuma yana cin mutum ne. Saboda haka, dole idan ana tafiya da shi a jere, ya kasance a gaba, domin da zarar mutum ya shiga gabansa, to zai cinye shi. Sai raƙumi na uku kuma wanda lafiyarsa kalau. A nan wannan falke ya fara tunanin yadda zai bi da waɗannan raƙuma, ba tare da wata matsala ta faru ba. Yaya zai tsara tafiyar?

¹³Wasu masu ne guda uku Allah ya yi su abokan juna. Shi dai da ma maye ba ya cin maye ɗan uwansa. Kowanne daga cikinsu yana da ɗa. Sai dai Allah ya yi ‘ya’yan nasu ba mayu ba ne. watarana sai tafiya ta kama waɗannan mayu uku da ‘ya’yansu. Suna tafe suna taɗi na abota. Amma kowannensu a ankare yake, ba zai taɓa kuskuren bazawa ko nan da can ya bar ɗansa kusa da ɗaya daga cikin mayun ba. Domin kuwa, da zarar uban ɗaya daga cikin ‘ya’yan baya kusa, to sunansa nama.

Suna cikin tafiya sai suka iso wani madaidaicin kogi. Ruwa ya kawo maƙil. Suka duba haka, sai ga jirgin ruwa, amma ba matuƙi. Sannan jirgin mutane biyu kaɗai yake iya ɗauka. Saboda haka, dole ne su riƙa shiga ta bibbiyu, sannan idan biyun da suka shiga suka haye, ɗaya daga cikinsu ya dawo da jirgin. Da haka da haka har su ketare gaba ɗaya. To a nan fa dambarwar take. Ta yaya ne za a yi hannan hayi ta bibbiyu ba tare da wani maye ya tafi ya bar ɗansa an cinye shi ba?

¹⁴Domin samun cikakken labarin, sai a duba Imam, A. A. (1994). *Magana Jari Ce 2*. Zaria: Northern Nigerian Publishing Company.

kare ya farga tare da taka rawar kidan zamani in har yana son tsira. Ba abin mamaki ba ne yadda ta kasance ‘yan siddabaru ke amfani da abubuwan da zamani ya zo da shi, domin gudanar da ayyukansu na siddabaru.¹⁵Da zarar wani sabon al’amari ya faru, ko wani sabon ci gaban zamani ya samu, sukan yi saurin amfani da wannan dama a matsayin hanyar damfara.¹⁶ Kafin al’umma su farga, har an ci kasuwa an watse. Ko da an gano wannan hanya daga baya, sai ya zamana cewa an yi abin nan ne da Hausawa ke cewa: “Ko yanzu kasuwa ta watse, Dankoli ya ci riba.”

Bunza, (2019)¹⁷ ya bayyana cewa, hanyar nuna jariri a cikin kwali (ko wani abu mai kama da wannan) da ‘yan damfara suke yi a da tsantsar siddabaru ce ba tsafi ba. A wancan lokaci, kan mutane bai waye da ‘yar bebin roba ba. ‘Yan siddabarun na samo bebin roba (‘yar tsana) su sanya cikin akwati ko kwali/bandiri (ko wani abu mai kama da wannan). Za su nemi wani ya leka ciki. Da zarar ya leka, sai ya tarar da ‘yar bebin nan. Nan kuwa zai razana. A tunaninsa, jinjirin gaske ne.

Da tafiya ta yi tafiya, musamman lokacin da aka fara samun bunkasar kimiyya da fasaha, sai ayyukan siddabaru da damfara suka dauki sabon salo. Masu amfani da siddabaru domin gudanar da ayyukan damfara sai suka sauya taku. Sun sanya rigar zamani game da ayyukansu na siddabaru da damfara. Wani babban abin lura amma shi ne, mafi yawan siddabaru da damfara da ake aiwatarwa ta hanyar amfani da kayayyakin zamani, to baki ne ga Bahaushu. Ya koye su ne daga bakin al’ummu na kusa da na nesa.

2.2.1 Waya (Kiraye-Kiraye Da Sakonnin Kar-ta-kwana)

A nan, na zaɓi na yi wa wannan fasalin fashin goro, wato fito da irin yadda masu siddabaru ke amfani da wayar salula ta hanyoyi mabambanta domin cimma muguwar manufarsu. Samuwar waya ya buɗe wani sabon babi a duniyar siddabaru da damfara. Manyan hanyoyin da damfarar waya ta kunsu su ne (i) kira, da (ii) sakon kar-ta-kwana. Misali (3):

1. Ana kiran mutum ta waya da sunan iskoki ne suka kira shi. Za a riƙa faɗa masa abubuwa game da tarihinsa da mu’amalarsa da wuraren hulɗatayyarsa da sauransu. Wannan zai ba shi mamaki matuƙa, a rashin sanin cewa da ma an riga an karance shi

¹⁵A nan musamman ana magana kan ‘yan damfara da ke amfani da siddabaru a matsayin tsaninsu na kai wa ga nasara.

¹⁶Za a iya tunawa da tarihin samuwar madubi ga Bahaushu. A lokacin da ya ga hotonsa cikin badubi, sai ya fashe da kukan tunanin ai babansa da ya daɗe da rasuwa ne. Wannan ya sa yake karɓar madubi a matsayin fufuren dukiya mai tarin yawa.

¹⁷An samu wannan bayani daga bakinsa, yayin da yake gabatar da lacca a ajin ‘yan digiri na biyu, a Cibiyar Nazarin Harsunan Nijeriya, Jami’ar Usmanu Danfodiyo, Sakkwato, ranar 24 ga watan Oktoba, shekara ta 2019.

sosai kafin a fara harkallar. Wani lokaci kuwa “da dan gari akan ci gari.” Yayin da aka samu bami ko kwadayayye, sai “a ci wawa a tashi.”

2. Ana iya kiran mutum da sunan cewa wani dan uwansa ya yi hadari ko ya shiga cikin wani mawuyacin hali. A irin wannan yanayi, za a nuna cewa ana bukatar wani abu na gaggawa kamar kuɗi ko wasu bayanai. Wanda bai yi farga ba, sai a yi farga da shi.
3. Akan turo wa mutum saƙo da sunan cewa daga wata ma'aikata ce, ko wani muhimmin wuri. Za a bukaci ya tura wasu bayanai masu muhimmanci kamar waƙanda suka shafi bayanankinsu da makamantansu. A irin haka ne za a damfari wanda bai mayar da hankali ba.

2.2.2 Intanet

Kafar intanet da ake ce wa “yanar gizo” ta kasance tamkar wata duniya ce mai zaman kanta. A kan intanet akwai tarin bayanankinsu da suka wuce sau shurin masaki. Akwai kuma kafafen sada zumunta iri-iri, kai ka ce garuruwa ne. Siddabaru da damfara a duniyar intanet sun shafi manyan bangarori guda biyu wato (i) kafafen intanet, da (ii) kafafen sada zumunta.

2.2.2.1 Kafafen Intanet

Tsangarwa, (2006:85) ya ba da ma'anar intanet da cewa: “Fasahar sadarwa ce da ta haɗa kwamfutoci a duniyance, kuma take ba su damar musayar bayanai a tsakaninsu.” Akan samar da kafafen intanet na yaudara. Ana musu tsari na musamman da za a iya amfani da su domin satar bayanankinsu duk wanda ya yi amfani da kafar. A shekarar 2012 an samu yawaitar wannan nau'in yaudara a tsakanin Hausawa. A lokacin kafar sada zumunta ta 2go na tashe. Ana yaudarar mutane da cewa za su samu kyautar kuɗi ko wani abu da ake kira *gocredit*, wanda da shi ne ake iya samun damar tura saƙonni a “ɗakuna” (rooms).¹⁸

A yanzu haka, a kullum sai an samu adadi mai yawa daga cikin Hausawa waƙanda aka tura musu saƙonni ta imel ko wata kafa ta intanet. Saƙon na iya kasancewa:

1. Ana iya ba da wani liƙau (link) da zai kai mutun zuwa wata kafar intanet ta daban. A can za a bukaci ya sanya wasu bayanai domin ya samu wani alfanu kamar kuɗi ko kwamfuta da sauransu. Bayanankinsu da ake nema na iya shafar na bankinsu ko lambobin sirrin imel dinsa, da dai makamantansu. Daga nan ne kuma za a yi amfani da waƙannan bayanai nasa wajen aikata masa ta'asa.

¹⁸A 2go, *rooms* sun kasance kafafe da ke haɗa mutane da dama. Duk wanda ya tura saƙo, to sauran mambobin za su gani. Mai *gocredit* ne kaɗai ke iya tura saƙo *arooms*.

2. Ana turo sakonni a matsayin ana neman a hada wata harkallar kasuwanci da wanda aka tura wa sakon. A nan, za a nuna masa cewa, kasuwanci ne da za a samu riba sosai. A wurin kwaɗayi, sai kuda ya mutu.
3. Sakon kuma na iya kasancewa na harkallar kuɗi kai tsaye. Misali, mai turo sakon na iya nuna cewa, shi mazaunin kasar waje ne. Yana son zuwa kasar da wanda aka turo wa sakon yake. A dalilin haka, yana son lambar asusun banki da zai turo wasu kuɗinsa masu yawa. Daga tunanin cin banza, sai banza ta sha mutum.

2.2.2.2 Kafafen Sada Zumunta

Wani babban abin da intanet ta zo da shi, shi ne kafafen sada zumunta. A yau akwai kafafen sada zumunta na intanet sama da dari uku. A kullum kuwa suna kara yawa ne. Fitattu daga cikin kafafen sada zumuntar da Bahausha ke amfani da su, sun hada da:

- i. Facebook.
- ii. Instagram.
- iii. LinkedIn.
- iv. Twitter.
- v. Whatsapp.

Kafafen na da muhimmanci matuƙa. Daga cikin amfaninsu akwai:

1. Suna taimakawa wajen sada zumunci cikin sauki.
2. Suna taimakawa wajen debe kewa.
3. Suna taimakawa wajen samun rubuce-rubucen ilimi.
4. Suna taimakawa wajen samun labaran abubuwan da ke faruwa yau-da-kullum.
5. Suna taimakawa wajen hada abota da soyayya.
6. Suna taimakawa wajen rage yawon banza.

Kamar yadda Bahausha ke cewa: “Kowane allazi da nasa amanu.” Daya daga cikin manyan matsalolin waɗannan kafafen sada zumunta shi ne harkokin siddabarun da ke kai wa ga damfara. Kamar yadda ra’in binciken ya ke (Karen bana shi ke maganin zomon bana), mafiya rinjayen masu amfani da kafafen sada zumunta ‘yan zamani ne. ‘Yan siddabarun da damfara na samun damar amfani da wannan kafa kasancewar:

- a. Talauci ya yi yawa a tsakanin samari Hausawa. Kodayake da man babban makamin damfara shi ne lasa wa mutum zuma a baki.

- b. Son banza na kara yawaita tsakanin matasa. Wannan ya shafi samari da ‘yammata. ‘Yan mata da ke da kwadayin abin duniya, an sha samun lokutan da aka lalata musu rayuwa ta hanyar yaudarar su ta kafar sada zumunta. Jaridar Hausa Legit ta rawaito labarin wata budurwa da aka damfara aka bata wa lokaci a kafar sada zumunta ta Facebook. Ta yi soyayya ta tsawon lokaci inda sai har ta niki gari ta tafi garin wanda suke tarayya ta kafar sada zumunta, sai ta tarar da cewa dan shekara 12 ne. Jaridar ta ce:

Budurwar ta bayyana cewa bayan zuwanta jihar Enugun ta gano cewa ashe da yaro dan shekara 12 take magana duk wannan lokacin. Usman, (2019: 1).

- c. Kwadayin tafiye-tafiye zuwa kasashen ketare ya yi yawa a zuciyar matasa. Miyagu kuwa suna amfani da wannan dama wajen damfarar matasan ta kafafen sada zumunta. Shafin gwamnatin Kanada ya wallafa jan kunne ga al’umma game da wannan nau’in damfara. Ya yi wallafar ranar 19/12/2018. A ciki an lissafo nau’ukan karairayi daban-daban da ‘yan damfara ke amfani da su ta kafafen sada zumunta domin damfarar al’umma.¹⁹
- d. A kafafen sada zumunta, akan samu sauƙin yada bayanai. Sannu a hankali har ya kai ga wanda zai fada tarkon ‘yan damfara. Kusan a kullum mutum ya bude kafafen sada zumunta, sai ya ci karo da ire-iren tarkunan da ‘yan damfara ke dānawa. Sun baza homa suna jiran makararren kifin da tsautsai zai ritsa da shi. A kasa an kawo misalan wasu daga cikin tarkunan ‘yan damfara da aka dauko daga kafar sada zumunta ta Whatsapp:

Hoto 1: Hoton da aka dauko daga Whatsapp wanda ke dauke da tarkon ‘yan damfara. Sun nuna cewa, yayin da mutum ya sanya wani adadin kudi, to zai samu ninkinsu.

¹⁹Za a samu wannan bayani a wannan kafa: <https://travel.gc.ca/travelling/health-safety/overseas-fraud>

2.3 Kamanceceniyar Siddabaru Da Damfarar Bahaushe Jiya Da Yau

Duk da cewa akwai bambance-bambance tsakanin ‘yan siddabarun gargajiya da na zamani, musamman masu amfani da siddabaru domin damfara, akwai kamanceceniya sosai a tsakaninsu. A kasa an zayyano wasu daga cikin waɗannan ɓangarori da suka yi tarayya:

1. Dukkaninsu na da manufa guda ne, wato damfare tunanin mutum ko mutane domin su samu abin da suke bukata daga gare su.
2. Dukkaninsu na amfani da ‘yan kore. Da ma dai akwai nau’o’in kore da ‘yan kore daban-daban.
3. Dukaninsu na amfani da kayan aiki. Wannan ya shafi sutura da jaka da makamantansu.
4. Dukansu na bin matakan nazartar halayyen al’umma musamman domin sanin ɓangarorin da suke da rauni. Hakan ne zai ba su damar bullo musu ta fuskokin da ba su tsammata ba.

2.4 Bambance-Bambancen Da Ke Tsakanin Siddabaru da Damfarar Bahaushe ta Jiya da ta Yau

Jad 1: Bammbacin da ke tsakanin Siddabarun Bahaushe Jiya da Yau ta Fuskar ‘Yan Siddabarun

	‘Yan Damfarar Gargajiya	‘Yan Damfarar Zamani
1.	Yawanci masu ilimin addini ne. An fi samun gardawa cikin harkokin siddabaru.	Yawanci masu ilimin boko ne da kuma ilimin sarrafa kwamfuta.
2.	Damfarar gargajiya ta fi faruwa gaba-da-gaba. Wato dole ɗan damfara ko ‘yan korensa su haɗu da wanda za a damfara.	Hanyoyin siddabaru da damfarar zamani na ba da damar a damfari mutum ba tare da an haɗu gaba-da-gaba ba.
3.	Yawanci baƙi ne ke damfarar gargajiya. Suna da salon “A ci wawa a tashi.”	Wanda ake tare da shi ma na iya bin hanyoyin damfarar zamani domin aiwatar da damfara, dalili kuwa shi ne, ba dole ne a gan shi ba.
4.	Suna amfani da kore da ‘yan kore na gargajiya, kamar mutane da dabbobi da tsuntsaye da sauransu.	Suna amfani da nau’ukan kore da ‘yan kore na zamani kamar kwamfutoci da sinadarai da injuna.

5.	Suna amfani da nau’o’in kayan aiki irin na gargajiya.	Suna amfani da nau’o’in kayan aiki irin na zamani, yawanci waɗanda suka shafi kimiyya da fasaha.
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Jad 2: Bambance-bambance tsakanin Siddabarun Bahausha Jiya da Yau ta Fuskar Ayyukan Siddabarun:

	‘Yan Siddabarun Gargajiya	‘Yan Siddabarun Zamani
1.	Dole sai an yi gaba-da-gaba da mutumin ko mutanen da za a yi wa siddabaru.	Ana iya aikata siddabaru har a damfari mutum ba tare da an yi gaba-da-gaba da shi ba.
2.	‘Yan kore sun haɗa da mutane da abubuwa da ana iya kallonsu kuma a taɓa su.	‘Yan kore sun fi shafar bayanai a kafafen sadarwa ko na’urori.
3.	Galiban suna aiwatar da siddabarun da wasu wasannin motsa jiki, saboda garin-da-garin da aka yi da waɗanda ake so a damfara.	Babu wani wasannin motsa jiki da ake aiwatarwa, saboda ba a tare ake da wanda ake so a damfara ba.
4.	Lissafo wasu kasashe da aka je tallar magani, da nufin nuna wa bami ba iya garinsu aka tsaya ba.	Akan yi kokarin Lissafo wasu kasashe da irin hanyoyin da suka yi amfani da su wajen harkokin zuba jari, da nufin kama hankalin mai son banza.
5.	Akwai salon jejjera magunguna tare da sanya layu da guraye (kurhuna) a jiki da nufin tauna tsakuwa domin aya ta ji tsoro.	Ba a maganar magani irin na ganyaye da saboda ba da su aka aje jigon damfarar ba. Sai dai karyar nuna wayewa da nuna ilimin boko da sanin ilimin kwamfuta da kuma yanar gizo.
6.	Bayar da kyautar magani musamman ga wanda ya nuna ya taɓa amfani da maganin (ɗankore) na daga cikin ɗabi’unsu.	Kasancewar ba a tare ake ido da ido da ɗan koren ba, babu batun bayar da kyautar abin da ake bayarwa.
7.	An fi aiwatar da shi a kasuwanni da dandali da kuma wurin da ake shagalin wasu bukuwa.	Ana aiwatar da shi ne a shafukan sada zumunta da sauran kafafen yanar gizo.

3.0 Siddabaru A Duniyar Kimiyya Da Fasaha

Sakamakon irin sauyawar da zamani ya yi, sai masu siddabaru suka dauki wani sabon salo domin su cigaba da damfarar al'umma. Kasancewar duniyar yau tana tafiya da ilimin kwamfuta tare da yanar gizo, sai suka koma suka tsirawa waɗannan hikimomi da ilmomi ido tare da nazartar yadda ake amfani da su. Wannan sai ya ba su damar kutsawa cikin ayyukan wasu ma'aikatan da ke da harkokin kuɗaɗe tare da daukar salailan da suke amfani da su wajen hulɗa da abokan hulɗarsu da nufin damfarar su. Abin ya kai ga suna iya yin sojan-gona ta hanyar turo sakon kar-ta-kwana ga al'ummomi daban-daban domin neman su bayar da kai bori ya hau. Abin ya kai ga akan turo wa masu hulɗa da bankuna da ma waɗanda ba sa hulɗar da bankunan sakonnin neman su tura lambobin asusun ajiyarsu na bankuna ko lambobin katin cirar kuɗinsu na banki da makamantansu, wannan sabuwar ɗabi'a ta tashi da masu son banza da yawa. Hausawa sun ce: "Sabon salo, in ji kaza da ta ji ana shika da daddare." A yau an fara samun 'yan damfara suna shiga irin ta ma'aikatan banki, su je gidan mutum su yi sallama da shi su nemi ya ba su lambobin asusun ajiyarsa na banki, kafin ya ankara sun tashi da shi.

A ɗaya ɓangaren kuma, suna kirƙirar hukumomi na ƙarya tare da tallata guraben neman aiki ga al'umma, wannan Fasaha da kimiyyar zamani tana shan wasu masulla.

4.0 Sakamakon Nazari

Hakika Bahausha ya dade yana ta'ammuli da siddabaru. Kusan abu ne mai wuya a iya tantance farkon lokacin samuwar wannan al'ada gare shi. Adabin Bahausha na dauke da hotunan wasu nau'ukan siddabarunsa. Ana samunsu cikin adabinsa na ka da kuma rubutattu. Sai dai siddabaru a Bahaushiyar al'ada bai kasance nau'i guda ba. Ya shafi na baka da kuma wanda ake gudanarwa a aikatace. Siddabaru ya kasance wani babban makami ga 'yan damfara. Tarin dabarbarun siddabaru suke amfani da shi wajen damfare tunanin waɗanda suke faman tatsa.

A yau kuwa, kimiyya da fasaha sun samar da wani sabon babi ga siddabarun Bahausha. Wannan ya fi shafar aikataccen siddabaru kai tsaye, wato siddabarun aiki ba na baka ba. A yau, na'urori irin su kwamfuta da wayar salula sun kasance ja-gaba a cikin 'yan koren 'yan siddabaru. Wannan ne kuma ya sa damfarar zamani ta dauki wani sabon salo. A yau ba sai baƙo ne ke iya damfarar al'umma ba. Dan gida ma na shiga rigar kimiyyar da fasaha, ya fake ya aiko zamba tambkar daga nesa. A irin wannan lokaci, har ma yakan iya shiga cikin 'yan jaje bayan an riga an ci wawa an tashi.

Yawanci damfarar zamani masu ilimin kwamfuta ke jagorancinta. Hausawa da ke cikin wannan harkar na daukar hannu daga al'ummu baƙi na kusa da na nesa. Wasu daga cikin salailan damfarar a finafinan Turawa ake nuna su. Wasu kuwa ana kallon su a tarurrukan nuna bajinta na duniya irin su *American Got Talent* da *British Got Talent* da *Arab Got Talent* da *Chinese Got Talent* damakamantansu. Wasu kuwa akan same su ne daga al'ummun kusa. Tuni jihar Lagos da ke tarayyar Nijeriya ta yi kaurin suna a wannan ɓangare na damfarar zamani.

4.1 Kammalawa

‘Yan siddabaru musamman waɗanda ke amfani da hanyoyin da siddabarun ya tattaro domin damfara sun kasance masu tsananin wayo. Bugu da ƙari kuma, suna da saurin nazartar yanayi tare da ƙoƙarin tafiya da zamani a koyaushe. Da zarar zamani ya buga tambari, suna kan gaba wajen taka rawarsa. Wannan ne ya sa suke da saurin samar da sababbin hanyoyin damfara musamman yayin da aka fahimci tsoffin da suke amfani da su. Kamar yadda ya kasance waɗanda suka fi faɗawa tarkon damfara kwaɗayayyu ne da ‘yan zalama, sai abin ya kasance “*Karen bana shi ke maganin zomon bana.*” Lura da haka, wannan bincike na ba da shawarar cewa:

1. A riƙa karantar da dabarun ‘yan siddabaru da damfara a manyan makarantu a matsayin kwas. Wannan zai taimaka wajen wayar wa jama’a kai tare da fitar da su daga sharrin tarko da ƙangin damfarar ‘yan siddabaru.
2. A riƙa gudanar da tarurrukan ƙara wa juna sani da wayar da kai dangane da siddabaru da damfara. Hakan zai taimaka wajen ƙara wayar da kan al’umma a matakin daidaiƙu.
3. Yana da kyau hukumomin da ke da alhakin daƙile harkokin almundahana da zambar kuɗaɗe su haɗa kai da sauran hukumomin gwabnati tare da ƙungiyoyi masu zaman kansu domin a gudu tare a tsira tare.
4. Akwai buƙatar hukumomin EFCC da ICPC da dangoginsu su haɗa kai da masana Harsunan Nijeriya domin fassara irin dabarun da suke ganowa ‘yan damfara na amfani da su cikin manyan Harsunanmu na Nijeriya.
5. Yana da kyau ‘yan majalisunmu na ƙasa da hukumomin shari’a su tsaya tsayin daka wajen ganin an sabunta dokokin ‘yan damfarar zamani tare da aiki da dokar ga duk wanda aka kama da hannu dumu-dumu yana aikata irin wannan ta’asa.

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